

Comparative Study of Lithium ion Batteries for Electrical Vehicles system

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Abstract

Current lithium ion battery technology is ready to revolutionize hybrid vehicles. Lithium iron phosphate batteries have twice the specific energy than that of nickel metal hydride batteries used in current hybrid vehicles. The batteries are also capable of enormous amounts of power, up to 3.3 kW/kg. This makes it possible for higher performance hybrids that are more appealing to the average consumer. The study presents a techno-economic comparison of the most commonly used battery technologies such as lead iron batteries and lithium cobalt batteries. Lead is a very heavy metal and therefore the research was done from many years to make better battery that is lighter in weight as well as it has improved power density. Then lithium became the logical choice to replace lead as it is the lightest metal available in the world. Lithium is not only light in weight but also highly reactive and for this reason pure lithium is never found in nature. In today's world Lithium Ion batteries are used in almost all gadgets including laptop, cell phone, camera, iPod and many more devices and hence they are very popular these days. They are one of the most energetic batteries available today which make them so popular. Our major concentration is on Lithium Iron Phosphate batteries and Lithium Cobalt batteries.

Keywords: Lithium ion Battery, Lithium Cobalt Battery, Power Characteristics.

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